

1 **CDKN3 is inactivated in response to ERBB2 growth factor inhibition and confers resistance to**
2 **trastuzumab.**

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8 Treatment failure in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is associated with progression to CNS metastasis.
9 We recently defined CDK10 activation as a compensatory mechanism following HER2 chemical
10 (pharmacologic) inhibition in humans with HER2+ breast cancer, and demonstrated separately that
11 quantitative determination of differential expression was sufficient for identification of synthetic lethality and
12 kinase addiction. We demonstrate here from study of RNA-sequencing measurement of total transcription
13 following pharmacologic inhibition of ERBB2 with two separate HER2 kinase inhibitors in human cancer
14 cells in vitro that the cell cycle inhibitor CDKN3 is compensatorily silenced in response to ERBB2
15 inhibition. Accordingly, CDKN3 repression was observed in vivo in HER2+ breast cancer patients who
16 failed treatment with trastuzumab (resistance). CDKN3 silencing compensates for ERBB2 inhibition. We
17 argue CDKN activation is a viable option for reversal or prevention of resistance to trastuzumab. CDKN
18 repression appears to be a central mechanism by which cancer cells evade cell cycle restriction.

19 Supporting data:

- 20 1. DLGAP5, PBK and HMMR are non-canonical CDKN3 targets.
- 21 2. CDKN3 is co-regulated with or directly regulates genes important for mitosis (the cell cycle)
22 including CDK1, AURKA, NUSAP1, SPC25 and NDC80.
- 23 3. Cyclins and cyclin-associated genes CCNB1, CCNB2, CCNA2 and CDC20 are also directly
24 regulated by and/or closely co-regulated with CDKN3.
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